

SOUND CULTURE OF SPEECH AS A LANGUAGE BASIS FOR MASTERING SPEECH SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDHOOD

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During preschool childhood, a child learns only one form of speech, oral speech. Oral speech is a sounding speech, the basis of which is the phonetic means of the language, namely: its phonetic system, intonation, stress.

Mastering the sound culture of speech in preschool childhood is personally and socially significant, since the oral form of speech is the only possible means for a preschooler to master the language system, as well as the only means of realizing the communicative function of language. Everyone knows the pattern: a child with an insufficiently formed sound culture of speech begins to experience difficulties in the process of communication, he is poorly understood by others, his peers often laugh at him. As a result, such a child consciously restricts his own speech communication, and his peers do not encourage him to do this: poorly speaking children are usually reluctant to play games, especially games involving the active use of language tools, the formation of speech skills.

A sufficient level of formation of the sound culture of speech in preschool childhood is also significant in terms of the child's readiness to study at school: the oral form of speech is widely used in educational activities, educational dialogue presupposes possession of the sound culture of speech, mastery of the written form of speech is possible only on the basis of possession of oral speech in accordance with the rules and norms of the language, because, mastering by literacy, the child masters the ways of transmitting the sounding speech on the letter.

Analyzing the main stages of mastering the sound culture of speech by a child during childhood, linguists, teachers present them as follows: from intuitive mastery

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The phonetic system and phonetic means of the native language in general, the child goes to the awareness of the means and conditions of sounding speech, to the primary ideas about the sounds of speech, about intonation, and then, in the process of learning at school, to the formation of concepts about the units of the phonetic system of the language, sounds, and phonetic means of the language, stress and intonation. The movement from the unconscious to the conscious, which distinguishes the whole process of mastering language and speech by a child, is also observed when mastering a certain level of the language system, the phonetic level. 3 groups of analyzers participate in mastering the phonetic system and phonetic means of the language: auditory, visual, speech motor. In order for a sounding unit to be reproduced by a child in his own speech, he needs to hear this sounding unit, see the articulation of an adult, perform a speech action himself, repeating this sound.

The inclusion of a wide range of analyzers in mastering the phonetic system of the language and phonetic means is due to the essential characteristics of speech activity: like any kind of activity, speech action can be mastered only in the activity itself.

Mastering the language means of oral speech begins in the first year of a child's life in communication with an adult. An adult provides the child with a speech environment, helps to isolate sounds and combinations of sounds in a continuous speech flow (a-a-a — lulling, ga-ga-ga — geese scream, ba-ba), thanks to which vowel sounds and labial consonants appear in the child's speech. This is an involuntary process: vowels are simple in articulation, articulatory differences in vowel sounds are associated with a change in the shape of the oral cavity and the degree of elevation of the tongue, the articulation of labial consonants is mastered by the child because he already has well-developed lip muscles and lips are mobile. From walking, the child is over he goes to babble¹, begins to perceive sound complexes as significant units, which is also possible only when interacting with an adult.

Early age is a kind of preparation in mastering language means and in the formation of speech skills, the child "talks" a lot, pronouncing sounds and sound complexes, thanks to which the speech apparatus begins to form. The task of an adult at this stage of a child's development is to provide the child with a base for mastering the phonetic system of the language, to help in the formation of the articulatory apparatus. To do this, it is not enough just to talk to the child. The child should see the articulation of an adult, an adult in conversation should use the sound complexes available to the child and, against the background of the positive emotional state of the child, encourage the baby to his own speech action, to repeat some complexes.

At an early age, the child masters the following groups of sounds: vowels, labial consonants, anterolingual consonants, posterolingual consonants, and, speaking of groups of consonants, it should be noted that the child first of all masters soft consonants, excessive palatalization is observed in his speech, which is also explained by the lack of formation of his articulatory apparatus, inability to control the mobile organs of speech an apparatus when the middle part of the tongue involuntarily rises to the hard palate, although when pronouncing consonants, this articulatory movement may be absent.

In the third year of life, the child masters almost all the sounds of the phonetic system of the language, except for the most complex: hissing, whistling, sonorous l, l, r, r. In most cases, the mastery of sounds is at the level of sound production, when a child can repeat the sound after an adult in an isolated position, for many sounds, the level of mastery can be defined as the level of automation when the child correctly pronounces the sound in words, phrases. The vocal apparatus is not always included in the sound pronunciation, so we can talk about such features of sound and word pronunciation in children of the third year of life as the replacement of posterior consonants with anterior consonants, the replacement of voiced consonants with deaf ones, the replacement of hard consonants with soft ones, the replacement of sibilant sibilants, the replacement of difficult-to-pronounce sonorous consonants with sounds simpler in articulation.

The noted features are explained not only by the level of formation of the articulatory apparatus, but also by the level of development of phonemic hearing, the ability to differentiate the sounds of the native language. Note that phonemic hearing begins to develop in a child already in the first year of life, its development always outstrips the development of the articulatory apparatus: first the sound must be heard, only then it will be pronounced. Therefore, the task of an adult is to improve the speech hearing of children, to develop hearing attention in preschoolers, to continue working on the formation of the articulatory apparatus.

To improve speech hearing and the formation of auditory attention, folk pedagogy, experts offer a variety of exercises, the content of which is aimed at teaching the child to listen to the sound: Guess who called; Guess what is making noise; Find an object by sound (Where is the dog barking?), etc., as well as highlight among the many sounds informatively significant. The improvement of the articulation apparatus is still associated with involuntary articulation exercises that a child performs at the prompting of an adult: playing with a typewriter, the child accompanies the game with the sound that the machine makes; the doll of the child cries, the dog barks. Voicing the surrounding objects, the child automates the sounds of his native language in speech activity, adapts the articulation apparatus to pronounce these sounds, in fact, thanks to similar exercises that appeared in the first year of the child's life, the articulation apparatus itself becomes.

The fourth year of life is different in that from intuitive, unconscious, involuntary mastery of the phonetic means of language, the preschooler passes to the awareness of this system, and above all the organs through which speech sounds are formed. Recognizing himself, the child also learns about the parts of the articulatory apparatus: lips, teeth, tongue, learns from the example of an adult to give a certain position to the movable organs of the articulatory apparatus, to fix articulatory movements. The main task facing an adult during this period of a child's life is to ensure the formation of the articulatory apparatus as a condition for mastering the phonetic system of the language. The main thing is not sound reproduction, but the presence of a mechanism that provides sound reproduction. The speech apparatus is part of the motor apparatus, so its development is impossible without the development of fine motor skills of the hands. The development of fine motor skills is promoted by finger games, special toys, self-service (putting on socks, buttoning buttons, etc.).

Speaking about the mechanism of sound formation, it is also necessary to remember that speech sounds are a phenomenon that by its nature does not differ from any sound as a physical phenomenon, this is the oscillatory movement of air particles. The formation of speech sounds is associated with the process of breathing. Speech sounds are formed when air moving from the lungs passes through the organs of the speech apparatus. The child knows how to breathe, this is a life-support condition, but does not know the technique of speech breathing, because the main respiratory movements in physiological breathing and speech breathing are distributed differently: in physiological breathing, the inhalation is longer than the exhalation, in speech breathing, the exhalation is performed as long as it is necessary to pronounce a certain segment of phonetic articulation of speech (usually syntagmas).

Thus, the work on the sound culture of speech of preschoolers ensures that preschoolers master the phonetic means of language and become aware of these means, which gives the child the opportunity to use speech as a means of communication and provides preparation for literacy. The content of the work on the sound culture of speech provides a preschooler with a transition from oral to written speech, awareness of the rules of written speech.

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